

TEACHING BUSINESS WRITING IN ENGLISH TO STUDENTS OF NON-LINGUISTIC SPECIALITIES

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Introduction. Today, business writing is one of the main key skills for highly qualified specialists in any field. Although electronic resources are quite enough to competently and stylistically compose a business document, in any case, having such a skill as business writing is very important, since companies on the market have different characteristics and standards in this area.

The ability to conduct business communication is often the main skill specified in the requirements for a job seeker and in fact it is difficult to find a company that does not conduct business correspondence with other companies, both partners and potential partners. However, as practice shows, it is not easy to find an employee who will competently and concisely write a business letter on behalf of the company in which he is employed to another company, since this skill in many educational institutions is given too little time and attention, or such a subject is absent altogether. Moreover, for a company it is very important not only to establish, but also to maintain economically mutually beneficial relationships, especially through properly established business contacts.

The aim of this study is to review features of teaching business writing in English to students of non-linguistic specialties and the practicality of introducing AI tools into the current educational system.

Problem statement. As a rule, students entering their first courses after graduating from secondary education do not have the proper grammatical skills and do not know how to formulate their thoughts in writing, which ultimately also creates a problem in teaching business writing. A business letter is a specific type

of letter, which distinguishes it from many other types. Such obvious differences are: language clichés; participial and infinitive phrases in sentences; special terminology; abbreviations; an extensive system of allied communications and many others. Brevity, content, lack of emotional coloring - these are the main distinguishing features of this type of writing.

When drafting business letters, spelling mistakes are the most frequent mistakes made by students, followed by punctuation and capitalisation. In punctuation using commas incorrectly when writing business letters ranks as the most common mistake made by students (21%). Omission, addition, misformation, and misordering were the main causes of the spelling, punctuation, and capitalization mistakes made by the students [1].

As some modern authors of the literature on the peculiarities of business writing note, for example, Astakhova L.A., given the lack of hours allocated to students for classes, a methodologically justified way to assimilate information is to optimize the material for active assimilation. The material selected by the teacher must be informatively sufficient to develop the necessary skills in drawing up business documentation for various purposes and complete content. Within time constraints, students need to pay attention to the most common types of business documents: letter of request; complaint letter; confirmation letter; office notes; certificates; offer letter [2].

When developing skills in working with business documentation among students of non-linguistic specialties, it is more logical, in our opinion, to choose three professionally significant communicative situations: documentation when concluding a transaction for the purchase and sale of goods; documentation required for employment; any business trip, especially foreign.

There are many stages to learning business writing. Krasavina O.E. notes that for students of non-linguistic specialties, three main stages of training can be distinguished: initial, intermediate and advanced. It is also important to take into account that each stage has its own characteristics and features. Such a feature is, for example, the use of templates, according to which it is possible to compose a

written business document of any form [3]. At the same time, it is worth conveying to the student that non-compliance with format and grammar can negatively affect the reputation of the company on whose behalf the correspondence is being conducted.

At the initial stage, everything is simple - we teach the student to fill out forms and questionnaires. To do this, it is enough to have a basic level of literacy. For example, filling out a questionnaire for participants in projects in the fields of culture and sports.

The middle stage is a little more difficult than the previous one. The student must master the structure of a business letter. This could be the date the letter was written, the address of the recipient and sender, the greeting, the body of the letter and its ending. It is also important to draw up appendices to the document, if any are implied. At this stage, the student must master the importance of using different greeting and ending options for a letter, and the stylistic difference between a business letter and other types.

For the middle stage, Mirazimova S.B. provides common greetings in official letters such as “Dear Ms. or Mr. Last name” or an alternative “Dear Sir or Madam” in case students don’t know the name of the recipient. Students can select their closing signature from the following examples: Sincerely; Sincerely yours; With appreciation; Thank you; Regards; Yours truly; Respectfully yours and write their name at the bottom of the letter [4].

The advanced level is the most difficult - here the student must learn to write a competent resume, email, and cover letters and offer letters.

When learning the ability to conduct business correspondence, you should pay attention to the choice of text material. Basic requirements: authenticity, communication, compliance with the chosen topic. From the very beginning of training, it is worth conveying to each student the existence of requirements for the style of business documentation, for example, about the rigor and structure of such text [5]. Often students who are accustomed to communicating on social networks use a familiar tone in the preparation of business documents, which is

unacceptable. This is where it becomes important to remind students that colloquial style should not be used in documents, nor should overly emotional words be used. Students should also understand that it is important to follow the rules of subordination in writing and know how to address employees and company management.

The student must master the formal business style of speech, since in modern business realities, even despite the presence of many ways of conducting correspondence, business correspondence is the main type of communication between partner companies. Even if all correspondence between companies is carried out via e-mail, it is important to understand that such a message must contain traditional forms of politeness and be concise and specific. The main problem when choosing this type of communication is the complete lack of confidentiality, since many companies have the practice of connecting all employees to corporate mail [6].

If we talk about some other methods of teaching business writing to students, we would like to draw attention to the trend of introducing artificial intelligence in many areas of education. Digital technologies do not stand still and large companies are already introducing them into their work. Communication is no exception, with artificial intelligence already making its way in a variety of ways. For example, the presence of voice assistants in smartphones, which cannot yet replace live communication, but this will be quite real in the near future.

Artificial intelligence in teaching business writing.

Artificial intelligence is also actively used in business communication. Such an example is the ability of the intellect to conduct a detailed analysis of speech, in which it can determine whether a person is emotionally disposed to communicate or not. This can help to identify the client's dissatisfaction or his complete satisfaction from receiving goods or providing services. Artificial intelligence is also capable of recognizing speech errors [7].

For example, QuillBot is an online AI writing tool to help students improve their grammar and paraphrase their writing. It offers several ways of paraphrasing

such as paraphrasing using equations or synonyms; Paraphrasing by changing the order of words in sentences; paraphrasing by changing the form of the word and paraphrasing by using active or passive sentences [8].

Yet another example is Grammarly. Grammarly is an online application that does thorough grammatical tests, covering everything from word spelling and sentence construction to basic grammar. This AI writing assistant shows corrections and suggestions to help students avoid mistakes in punctuation and capitalisation. By following Grammarly's suggestions learners can increase the quality of their writing [9].

A research study was conducted to investigate the effectiveness of an AI-powered writing tool in a group setting for second-year postgraduate English students in the context of academic writing in English. The results of using Grammarly writing tool indicate enhancement of academic mood, engagement, and self-efficacy at the post-intervention [10].

In his article, McVey Ch. stated that with the development of technologies and integration of AI tools writing at universities has also been changing. Therefore, we should embrace this change by going beyond traditional academic essay and letting students experiment with their writing across many media forms [11].

It is also possible to use artificial intelligence for pedagogical purposes. With its emergence and development, new opportunities are opening up that can improve the learning process and improve the quality of education. The introduction of such a method into education can help in creating unique educational programs; speaking of business communication, it can help students assimilate and structure the information they receive in their heads much faster.

Third example is ChatGPT. It is a chatbot that can regenerate responses and provide accurate input to students. ChatGPT was given a real business case to compose 150 words email for the produce/create business writing question. The email was graded according to a well-established email writing rubric and received average grade. It had elements of copying without citing sources from

internet sites, lack of details and follow-up solutions. So, the provided email can be seen as a template for business writing rather than customized electronic mail [12].

Also, systems such as artificial intelligence can automate the routine work of a teacher, which takes a lot of time. In this way, the teacher will be able to devote more time to the student and the problems that arise during the learning process.

Conclusion. Thus, summarizing all of the above, it can be noted that currently teaching business writing to students of non-linguistic specialties is a pressing issue that requires different approaches. It has its own characteristics and requirements that are mandatory in this process. By analyzing works of various authors, it was found that many students struggle with formal language conventions such as proper etiquette and structuring that leads to many errors in grammar, spelling and punctuation. In this work we propose the use of artificial intelligence which can not only help teachers structure the learning process but also assist students in checking their works for any mistakes and increasing the quality of their writing. Implementation of AI tools in our educational system will help to create a workforce that is technologically savvy and better equips students for the demands of their particular fields.

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